

METHODS OF FORMATION OF PHONETIC SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the consideration of the content, as well as the goals of the formation of phonetic skills, the main approaches to teaching the phonetic aspect of the language.

Key words: phonetic skills, phonetic aspect, pronunciation skills, sounds, interference, communication.

МЕТОДИКА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФОНЕТИЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ ПРИ
ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена рассмотрению содержания, а также целей формирования фонетических навыков, основных подходов к обучению фонетической стороне языка.

Ключевые слова: фонетические навыки, фонетический аспект, произношения, звуки, интерференция, общение.

In the new millennium, English remains one of the most important means of international communication. Language universities are faced with the task of training specialists who possess both professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and are capable of foreign language communication by means of the English language. One of the main tasks of teaching English to future generation is to ensure the establishment of business contacts with foreign partners, to negotiate in a foreign language, for which it is necessary to possess a foreign language speech culture, to be able to speak coherently, logically, phonetically correctly formalize a statement in accordance with a communicative intention.

The formation of students' pronunciation skills directly affects the speed and strength of assimilation of the received material, as well as contributes to the development of oral speech, reading and writing. According to the methodologists, the conditions that have a great impact on the successful learning of the phonetic side of the language include the determination of difficulties in reproducing and perceiving sounds, the detection of zones of positive transfer and interference, and the formation of speech hearing.

Language competence presupposes the possession of language knowledge. In linguistic competence, A.M. Shakhnarovich identifies levels corresponding to the levels of the language system: phonetic, lexical, grammatical (word-formation and grammatical sublevels) [Shakhnarovich, 1997]. The problem of the formation of the phonetic level of language competence, in particular the development of phonetic skills, is very relevant today.

It is especially acute at the initial stages of learning English language, in particular at primary school age. Phonetic education the material in a secondary school involves students mastering all the sounds and sound combinations of a foreign language; mastering stress and basic intonation models (antonyms) of the most common types of simple and complex sentences [Lebedinskaya, 2003].

Learning any language always starts with phonetics. Teaching a foreign language to children also traditionally begins with the production of sounds. Children learn spoken language much faster than adults. Correct phonetics creates psychological comfort for children in another language. At primary school age, children make mistakes naturally, successfully overcoming them and, thus, learning much faster. During this period, children have a pronounced ability to imitate.

There are several criteria for selecting the phonetic minimum [Lebedinskaya 2003]:

1) according to the degree of complexity of the phonetic phenomenon, the object of special assimilation in teaching pronunciation is only those phonetic phenomena that pose certain difficulties for students;

2) according to the needs of communication – to a minimum, first of all, sounds are included, which perform a meaning-distinguishing function in speech.

3) according to the norm – all possible deviations from the norm are removed from the phonetic minimum, and the object of training is a complete the style of exemplary literary pronunciation (the pronunciation of radio and television announcers/commentators is taken as the standard).

There are certain requirements for teaching pronunciation to students. According to V.M. Filatov, the main requirements for pronunciation are phonemicity, that is, the degree of correctness of the phonetic design of speech sufficient for the interlocutor to understand it, and speed, that is, the degree of automation of pronunciation skills, which allows students to speak at a normal pace (130-150 words per minute) [Filatov 2004].

In school, it is very difficult to achieve the accuracy and authenticity of students' pronunciation, so the pronunciation requirements students are determined based on the principle of approximation. For this purpose, the volume of phonetic learning is limited, and a slight

decrease in the quality of pronunciation of individual sounds and intonation patterns is also allowed. Approximated pronunciation is a pronunciation in which, as in literary pronunciation, there are no phonological errors, but which, unlike literary pronunciation, allows non-phonological errors that do not interfere with understanding spoken utterances and what is read aloud in this language [Filatov 2004].

When teaching foreign pronunciation, it should be borne in mind that students already possess the sound means of their native language and, in many cases, a second language. On the one hand, it helps in mastering the pronunciation of a new (foreign) language, on the other hand, it causes certain difficulties caused by interference of the native language.

Given the difficulties faced by school student in mastering English pronunciation, it is advisable to use imitative and analytical methods simultaneously in the learning process (explanations and analysis should be used to the extent that they can be useful for students to understand the features of the phonetic phenomenon and facilitate its assimilation). This method is called analytical-imitative [Astafieva 2006].

You can add game elements to any type of activity in the lesson, and then even the most boring activity takes on an exciting form. This is especially true of the aspect of teaching phonetics of a foreign language. Among the games aimed at better perception, it is the phonetic features of a foreign language that distinguish:

- games for the formation of the correct articulation of English sounds language;
- games for the formation of phonemic hearing skills
- games that promote better assimilation of transcription signs [Tretyak 2013].

There are three main approaches in the methodology for teaching the phonetic aspect of a language. Modern teaching methods are based on a combination of these two methods. Let's look at them in more detail.

An articulatory approach. Proponents of this approach rely on the following provisions:

- a) you should start learning a foreign language by setting sounds, and for this you need an introductory phonetic course;
- b) each sound must be carefully worked out separately;
- c) to ensure the purity of pronunciation, it is necessary to study the work of the organs of articulation when pronouncing each sound;
- d) the formation of pronunciation and auditory skills is separate.

In conclusion we can say that in terms of pronunciation training, the teacher should adjust the phonetic skills that students already have in accordance with the phonetic system of the English

language and supplement it with those pronunciation elements that are absent in the native language of elementary school students. It is advisable to use an analytical and imitative method in the learning process.

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